

Local Government in Switzerland

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Switzerland: An Introduction

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It is not possible to make generalized statements on the relations between canton and municipalities for all of Switzerland. In the Swiss federal system, the cantons (and not the Confederation) determine the status and role of municipalities. Each canton has its own way to organize relations with municipalities, allocate competences and organize municipal finances. Thus, intergovernmental relations differ largely among the cantons. Because of historic and cultural reasons, the cantons of the French speaking part have a more centralistic approach, while municipalities in the eastern and central part of Switzerland show a more decentralized structure when it comes to the allocation of tasks. Our examples mainly refer to the Canton of Berne and its relation to the Bernese municipalities. The canton is perceived as a bridge builder between the German and the French speaking cantons and their traditions. Regarding municipal autonomy it might be considered as a kind of Swiss average. The Canton of Berne is one of the biggest cantons in terms of territory as well as the number of residents (around 1 Mio, 16.3 per cent foreign passport holders according to the census of 2018). The City of Berne is the capital of the canton as well as of the Swiss Confederation. Socially and politically, the canton is quite heterogeneous: relatively big urban and peri-urban areas are coupled with reasonably big rural and mountainous areas that are thinly populated. Around 10 per cent of the residents are mainly speaking French, the big majority are German speakers. All these elements make the Canton of Berne an interesting object of observation.

In Switzerland there is hardly any public task that is exclusively performed by municipalities, without any central steering or co-financing, and the distribution of responsibilities is constantly evolving. In all important policy areas there is a sharing of competence that requires a cooperative set-up between cantons and municipalities at various levels. As a rule, the canton focuses on the adoption of the legal framework, establishes a control system and exercises oversight. With the increasing mobility and the evolving complexity of public tasks it is not surprising that generally, the central competences are increasing and the scope of action of municipalities tend to be decreasing. The principle of subsidiarity (Article 5(a) of the Federal Constitution) is providing (federal) orientation for the allocation of competences, stating that tasks should be performed as close to the population as possible. Thus, the primary schools, social welfare, local spatial planning, public security, local transport, water supply and waste management are most often in the competence of municipalities – but there are still many federal and cantonal rules and standards that are to be considered by municipalities.

Financial equalization is an important pillar of the Swiss political system, allowing for financial collaboration and cooperation among cantons and municipalities. At the level of the Confederation it focuses on the equalization of resources as well as the equalization of financial

burdens between cantons. The same idea of equalization is also applied at cantonal level, between municipalities. Regarding the allocated tasks, the cantonal regulations hardly make any difference between municipalities that, in terms of inhabitants, tend to be bigger in urban areas and smaller in rural areas. The cantonal specifications and standards are the same, the cantonal controlling and oversight does not differentiate between urban or rural, big or small municipalities. However, the Canton of Berne is contributing to the financing of municipal tasks in many respects. The cantonal share is calculated according to the constitutional principle of ‘financial equivalence’: The canton pays what it is commissioning. For example, the canton has adopted a relatively dense regulation concerning the salaries of primary teachers, the curricula and the required lessons for primary schools – thus, the canton pays 70 per cent of the salary expenses for primary school teachers. The rest of the salary expenses are financed by the municipalities, through their own tax income.

Today, municipalities with low financial capacities would not be able to finance their tasks by their own tax income. Thus, a horizontal equalization scheme has been developed. This scheme is mainly alimeted by payments of well-off municipalities but the canton is also contributing funds. The payment scheme for equalization of resources is meant to allow for an adequate (but not full) equalization of standards among municipalities, independent of their financial capacities. In addition, the equalization of burdens aspires to balance specific burdens on the municipalities that are caused by social demography, geographical challenges (for example, the cost of an extensive water supply or road system in a thinly populated rural area), or specific tasks of urban centres (*Zentrumslasten*). The equalization payments are calculated based on a cantonal law and decided upon by the cantonal government, taking into account a very differentiated set of parameters that is adjusted regularly. The equalization system in the canton of Berne has grown over the years into a complex body of horizontal and vertical, direct and indirect, general and sectorial mechanisms. The impact of the equalization scheme on the canton and (urban and rural) municipalities is regularly evaluated and assessed in the light of the context dynamics, and adjustments are frequently thematized and discussed in the political debate..

Every Swiss municipality is participating in intermunicipal cooperation in multiple ways and forms and obtains services from third parties. From the political point of view as well as from the accountability perspective, there is hardly any difference whether the (public) task is performed by the municipality itself, in cooperation with other municipalities or by third parties. In the Canton of Berne, in average, around half of the municipal budgets are spent by own activities, around a third of the budgets go to legally autonomous bodies owned by the municipalities (such as associations of municipalities, or shareholder companies owned by municipalities), and one sixth of the budget is spent for buying services from third parties. Smaller and even medium size municipalities have difficulties to perform their tasks according to the required quality standards and the cooperation with other municipalities or the private sector allows them to improve their professional performance. However, in many cases, cooperation is not cheap – it will not lead to lower costs as it is often hoped for.

Intermunicipal cooperation is mainly organized in two legal forms: the association of municipalities and the assignment of one municipality to perform tasks of others. The association of municipalities is a legally autonomous municipal body that is foreseen by the cantonal municipal law. Individual municipalities commission this body to fulfill a certain task. The association is organized in a legislative and an executive body and acts according to a set of rules that must be adopted by the participating municipalities. Essential changes to the delegated tasks or the funding parameters cannot be adopted by the majority within the association against the will of participating municipalities. This form of cooperation has proved itself many times. However, the challenge is that the steering of the associations is often mediated through individual representatives in their decision-making bodies, there is often a certain self-reinforcing momentum, and municipal authorities have difficulties to have their voices as owners heard. The second legal form is the contracting of one municipality to fulfill tasks on behalf of other municipalities. The advantages of the association (for example, the participation of the delegating municipalities in decision-making processes) can also be reflected in the contract. The advantage of this form is that the fulfillment of the task is embedded in an existing municipal set-up and can profit from existing professional structures and administrative services. While these forms of intermunicipal cooperation are ruled by public law, municipal tasks are often also delegated to companies that are formally under private law, for example joint-stock companies or cooperatives that run a regional sports facility on behalf of various municipalities. Here again, the steering and the ensuring of accountability can be challenging. Increasingly, the participating municipalities do no longer engage in the steering boards of such companies but are agreeing among themselves on an owner strategy that they then commission to the private company for execution.

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